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Breaking Barriers: Unveiling Narratives of Disability and Gender in Indian Digital Literature

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Abstract:

Disability as a theme, image, or character underrepresents in Indian Literature in English. Disabled people's writing also could not make the waves in mainstream Indian Literature. With the emergence and popularization of social media platforms, there has been a notable increase in digital media writing on various topics. However, exploration of marginal social categories, such as disability, gender, and caste, remains relatively limited. Nevertheless, there are promising writings emerging, particularly in the realm of disability.

Disability Studies propound the social model, where disability is seen as a 'social construct,' contrary to the medical model, which views disability as 'something that needs to be cured,' and 'dis-abled'. The perception of disabled people as either helpless or heroic is an oversimplified and stereotypical representation that can contribute to marginalization. Self-representation of disabled women is deconstructing it.

In this article, we are examining “‘Fake it till you make it’: Surviving the terrifying loneliness of being a young person with an amputation” by Parvathy Gopakumar, a self-narrative, written by disabled women featured in "Skin Stories: Essays on Sexuality, Disability, and Gender." This digital publication edited by Shreya Ila Anasuya. The study exclusively

includes the narrative of Parvathy, who uses a prosthetic hand. It offers a firsthand perspective on the impact of accessibility on her daily experience. Her story challenges traditional perspectives on mobility, embodiment, and societal structures, inviting a nuanced exploration of accessibility, identity, and the intersections of gender and disability with various aspects of life. Parvathy Gopakumar's memoir offers a compelling counter-narrative to the prevalent societal norms that often marginalize individuals with disabilities, challenging and dismantling the stereotypes and stigmas associated with disability.

Keywords: Self-representation, Digital Literature, Counter-Narrative, Identity, Disability, Gender.

Digital humanities is a field that combines traditional literary studies with computer technology. By using digital tools, researchers can examine and understand cultural materials, such as English literature, in new ways. It's a dynamic field that bridges the gap between traditional humanities and the digital world. 1

As Alan Liu observes, the digital humanities "focuses on documents and texts", distinguishing itself from other digital research fields. This emphasis on traditional humanities disciplines and older media aligns with the digital humanities' focus on preserving and studying historical materials and cultural heritage(409)

By using computational methods to analyze and interpret cultural artifacts, digital humanities offer new perspectives and insights into many disciplines. From literary studies to art history, this interdisciplinary approach allows researchers to ask complex questions, uncover hidden patterns and develop new methods. With digital tools and [ST1] techniques, scholars can access and analyze massive datasets, create interactive visualizations and engage with audiences in ways never before possible. As the digital world continues to change, digital humanities is at the forefront of research and offers so much to our understanding of the human experience.

The intersection of storytelling, personal narratives, digital humanities, and cultural memory offers a rich terrain for exploration. Digital humanities, with its capacity to process and analyze vast amounts of data, has become a powerful tool in "reconstructing cultural memory". (Fu, Mahony, and Liu,1522)

This paper analysing “Fake it till you make it’: Surviving the terrifying loneliness of being a young person with an amputation” by Parvathy Gopakumar, featured in "Skin Stories: Essays on Sexuality, Disability, and Gender." This digital publication edited by Shreya Ila Anasuya. The "Skin Stories: Essays on Sexuality, Disability, and Gender " is included with personal narratives regarding sexuality, gender and disability and intersection of all. This paper critically analyse the self-representation of disabled women from Indian setting and their life as a person with disability.

Parvathy Gopakumar's memoir offers a critical analysis of the self-representation of disabled women in India. It is deconstructing the ‘disabling’ -societal norms. She is questioning and thereby breaking down the stereotypes and stigmas associated with the disability.

By deconstructing societal norms and challenging stereotypes, it provides us with a more complex view of the challenges faced by persons with disabilities. Gopakumar’s work shows the intersection of disability with other marginalized identities like gender. It challenges the prevailing narrative of disability as a passive state. Her memoir is a counter narrative centered around agency and resilience and contributes to the larger discourse of disability representation in Indian literature.

By deconstructing the notion of "deviant" bodies, Gopakumar challenges the boundaries established by the normative. Her lived experience disrupts the idea that disability signifies a lack of authority or agency. As Rosemarie Garland Thomson suggests, the normate's power relies on the existence of these "marked bodies" – Gopakumar's memoir disrupts this dynamic by claiming agency and reclaiming her narrative (1997,08). Through her writing, Gopakumar demonstrates the limitations and biases inherent in the concept of the "normate," ultimately dismantling the power it holds.

The "normate" sheds light on how societal constructions of ability and disability perpetuate inequalities (08). The "normate," as she defines it, is not a specific person but rather an idealized figure embodying societal expectations of physical and cognitive ability.

A significant portion of existing scholarship portrays individuals with disabilities as marginalized members of society. Authors often substantiate these claims through personal anecdotes and real-life experiences. Conversely, digital humanities, particularly memoirs and narratives explored in collections like "Skin Stories: Essays on Sexuality, Disability, and Gender," tend to depict individuals with disabilities as integrated members of the community.

The title "Skin Stories: Essays on Sexuality, Disability, and Gender" is very significant. Skin Stories encapsulates the myriad narratives etched upon the largest human organ. Beyond its biological function as a protective barrier, skin is dynamic canvas reflecting our identities, experiences, and histories. Beyond its physical and cultural implications, skin has become a powerful medium of expression.

This paper exclusively includes the narrative of a woman named Parvathy, who uses a prosthetic hand. It offers a firsthand perspective on the impact of accessibility on her daily experiences. Her real-life story challenges traditional perspectives on mobility, embodiment, and societal structures, inviting a nuanced exploration of accessibility, identity, and the intersections of gender and disability with various aspects of life. In the broader sense, this paper investigates how both gender and disability are self-represented by women in India in the contemporary popular online medium.

Personal narratives have been the bedrock of human expression, giving us deep insights into individual and collective lives. Traditionally, the dissemination of these narratives was controlled by gatekeepers, such as publishers and editors, who held significant power over which stories should be made available to the public. As a result, marginalized voices were often silenced or underrepresented.

In "Digital Storytelling: Unleashing the Power of Narrative in the Digital Age", Bakhtiyari and Behzadi state that This landscape has changed significantly with the introduction of digital humanities. Digital technologies have made storytelling more accessible by offering platforms for invention, distribution, and preservation. A more inclusive and representative cultural record has been fostered by the democratization that has enabled people from different backgrounds to share their experiences without the need for intermediaries. (2023)

Digital platforms have lowered the barriers to entry for personal narrative creation. Individuals can now author, edit, and publish their stories with relatively easily, bypassing traditional publishing channels. This has led to many personal narratives and a wide range of perspectives on human experience and modern life. Furthermore, digital humanities tools and methods have allowed us to analyze and interpret these narratives and produce new knowledge and cultural understanding.

Digital humanities have the power to amplify marginalized voices. By providing a platform for the narratives and stories of the unheard, these technologies create a more inclusive

public sphere. And digital preservation means these stories will not be lost to history, so future generations can learn from the past and build on what came before.

Despite the challenges of online harassment and misinformation, the digital humanities provide valuable support for personal narratives, allowing individuals to share their stories more widely. Digital Humanities offer a space for diverse voices to be heard and valued, and can lead to empathy, understanding and social change. By offering a space for diverse voices to be heard and valued, these technologies have the potential to foster empathy, understanding, and social change.

Life writing has traditionally been a space for exploring the layers of the human experience. However, the representation of disability within this genre has been marginalized. For centuries, narratives focused on the people with disability were often medicalized, pathologized, or simply omitted, reinforcing societal stereotypes and misconceptions.

Disability life writing emerged as a powerful counter-narrative, challenging these representations and offering alternative perspectives. The Life writing of disabled people is significant form of 'self- representation' and it is also redefining the cultural representation of disability. Disabled people by writing particularly their own autobiographies, "assumed the initiative in representing themselves".

Thomas G Couser argues that Disability auto biographers typically begin from a position of marginalization, belatedness, and pre-inscription. Yet one can see why autobiography is a particularly important form of life writing about disability: written from inside the experience in question, it involves self-representation by definition and thus offers the best-case scenario for reevaluation of that condition (458)

The intersection of personal narratives and digital humanities offers a potent space. Due to the development of digital tools and open platforms, researchers can explore new insights into the experiences of disabled individuals, challenge ableist representations, and create more inclusive digital environments.

The disability is a culturally fabricated narrative of the body, similar to what we understand as the fictions of race and gender. The ability/disability system produces subjects by differentiating and marking bodies. (Hall, 17) Disability Studies challenge the conventional perspective of disability, moving away from the medical model and instead adopting the social model, which views disability as a 'culturally fabricated narrative of the body.' In contrast to

the medical model, which often labels disabled individuals as 'dis-abled' and 'one in need of a cure', this approach considers the body as an embodiment of social meaning. Therefore, Disability Studies is a comprehensive examination of the stigma faced by individuals with disabilities and how they respond to the social exclusion they encounter. Normalcy and disability are binaries that exist in society, privileging able-bodied section.

Helen Meekosha explores the gendered experiences of disabled individuals, highlighting that 'sometimes, disabled people are represented as without gender, as monsters. Stereotypes are artifacts of culture. Gender stereotypes interact with disability stereotypes, constitute a deep matrix of gendered disability in every culture. The gendered experience of disability reveals sustained patterns of difference between men and women. Disabled women face multiple subjugations. Upali Chakravarty argues that the image of disability may be intensified by gender. "For women, a sense of intensified passivity and helplessness, for men a corrupted masculinity generated by enforced dependence." (Meekosha 2014,28, Gerschick 2000) Disabled women are often considered asexual and childlike. Often, well-meaning overprotective families can create 'learned helplessness in the disabled person preventing him/her from being autonomous (Ghai,2015,12).

"Disabled women negotiating their impaired bodies and internalising sociocultural constructions of the "normal" female body." According to Nandini Ghosh, the body is understood as socially constructed, interpreted and experienced, and it becomes a physical site from and through which a person knows and interacts with the social world. The possession of a body with specific features within society becomes crucial for everyday recognition and identification of persons as well as for interpreting individuals' interactions with their bodies and through their bodies with the world around them (Ghosh 2015: Turner 1996; Davis 1996; Shakespeare 2003)

Ableist ideologies operate within culture through legal, medical, political, and literary discourses of exclusion, portraying the physically disabled body as an embodiment of corporeal insufficiency and a repository of societal anxieties regarding control and identity.

Accidental disability is a term used to describe a disability that occurs unexpectedly due to an accident or unforeseen event. As the term suggests, the disability occurs accidentally. Accidental disability contrasts with congenital disabilities, which are present from birth, or progressive disabilities, which worsen over time.

Disability is frequently associated with fatalistic and religious interpretations for two primary reasons. Firstly, a lack of awareness surrounds the medical aetiology (cause) of disabilities. Secondly, a stereotypical perspective persists, viewing disability as a tragedy and disabled individuals as the "other." However, when it comes to acquired disabilities, the focus often shifts to blaming the individual's actions and decisions.

In accordance with this idea, there are numerous models have been employed to understand and address disability. Each model offers a distinct perspective on the nature of disability and its implications for individuals and society. The medical model positions disability as a biological or psychological impairment residing within the individual. It focuses on diagnosis, treatment, and cure, often neglecting the impact of environmental factors. The charity model views people with disabilities as objects of pity and charity, emphasizing their dependency and vulnerability. This model often reinforces power imbalances and stereotypes.

An acquired disability, on the other hand, refers to any physical or mental disability acquired during one's lifetime due to an accident, some disease, environmental factors, or the like. Acquired disabilities can occur suddenly or chronically and can be physical or invisible. Amputation is an example of acquired disability.

An amputation can abruptly transform an individual's identity from that of a 'normal' human being to a person with a disability. Ironically, this sudden shift often leaves the newly disabled person confused and uncertain about how to live the 'new life'. While societal perceptions frequently characterize In most cases, society views individuals with disabilities as as 'others' who live on the outside periphery of society and are considered abnormal; however, the authentic experience of these people is usually overshadowed by stereotypes. This is analogous to the reality check we experience when confronted with a real-life thief. In such a situation, we typically react with surprise and interrogation. Individuals with disabilities may feel burdened by their condition, as if encumbered by heavy, unfamiliar armor. This newfound reality can be overwhelming, forcing a profound adjustment to their lives. Individuals with disabilities, especially women with disability, often find themselves burdened by the weight of societal stigma, which can be as oppressive as a physical constraint. This devaluation of their identity necessitates a profound adjustment, as they grapple with a new and often isolating reality.

"Fake it till you make it": Surviving the terrifying loneliness of being a young person with an amputation" is the poignant title under which Parvathy Gopakumar offers a condensed

narrative of her life. The author candidly recounts how a traumatic accident irrevocably altered her existence, resulting in a disability. She vividly describes the incident as a catalyst that transformed her life within a minute.

Gopakumar elaborates on the abrupt onset of her disability, describing how a single accident resulted in the amputation of her hand. She recounts the experience as a sudden and overwhelming transformation: "Without me even realizing what was happening, my world changed. I awoke days later to the grim reality of a bus having run over my right hand, necessitating amputation below the elbow."

Surprisingly, Parvathy's initial response to this life-altering event marked by resilience rather than despair. Unlike older individuals who might dwell on lost opportunities or future challenges, she was relatively unaffected by such concerns. While acknowledging the inherent discomfort of beginning anew, she emphasizes the absence of sadness during this period.

"I was rather quick to cope with the change; worries that an older person would have had, like what opportunities I might miss, or how I'd 'manage' my life, or whether someone would want to marry me didn't cross my mind at all. I felt the discomfort that accompanies starting a new life, but I wasn't sad."

Parvathy's narrative demonstrates her capacity to adapt to the physical changes she underwent. Her assertion of not experiencing sadness post-amputation suggests an initial resilience in the face of her impairment. However, it is essential to note that the absence of immediate emotional distress does not necessarily equate to a complete lack of challenges or psychological impact. Parvathy's positive mindset reinforced by the support of her schoolmates. Upon returning to school, she met with an outpouring of affection and acceptance. Parvathy's poignant observation of being "patted on the remaining arm" underscores the nonchalant manner in which her classmates treated her disability, suggesting a remarkable absence of stigmatization within her social circle. Despite her outward resilience, Parvathy experienced profound emotional turmoil as a consequence of her loss. Her initial optimism challenged when casual conversations among her peers revealed the harrowing perspectives of their families. These discussions, marked by a stark contrast to the support she had received from her classmates, exposed the deeply entrenched societal attitudes towards disability. "(...) 'So, my father was telling my mother how it would've been better if Paru just died rather than go through all of this,'."

Gopakumar's narrative offers a profound exploration of societal attitudes towards disability. The candid exchange she recounts with her friends about their parents' reactions to her amputation reveals a stark contrast between the perspectives of children and adults. While children, with their limited societal conditioning, exhibit a remarkable acceptance of difference, adult perspectives often cloud by ingrained biases and fears.

The friends' parents, as representatives of a broader societal mindset, expressed a preference for death over a life with impairment. This tragic viewpoint underscores the deep-rooted stigma surrounding disability. Their concerns highlight the societal construction of disability as a "disabling situation" rather than a variation of human experience. Furthermore, the lens of gender intersects with this narrative, revealing the additional challenges faced by women with disabilities who often expect to conform to specific societal roles. Parvathy's strength and determination to lead a meaningful life defy such perceptions. Her story powerfully demonstrates that disability does not limit one's potential.

Beyond the physical limitations imposed by impairment, Parvathy's friends' parents likely expressed concern over her ability to fulfil traditional gender roles. Society often expects women to be primary providers and a disability can be perceived as hindering this expectation. This viewpoint reinforces the harmful synergy between ableism and sexism, where both societal biases limit the potential and opportunities for women with disabilities.

Ultimately, this open dialogue catalyzes critical reflection on societal attitudes and practices. The situation emphasizes the necessity of removing of harmful stereotypes and the safeguarding of the rights of others in order to build a better world where people with disabilities are valued for what they can offer.

Lennard J. Davis argues that disability is not inherent to the individual but rather a social construct. He posits that:

"The 'Problem' is not the person with the disabilities, the problem is the way that normalcy constructed to create 'the problem of the disabled person' " (Davis,1995)

Parvathy Gopakumar's narrative highlights a crucial aspect of disability studies - the dynamic interplay between personal experience and societal constructs. Initially, her positive outlook suggests a resistance to internalizing the limitations others might project onto her. She describes herself as "behaving as normal," potentially indicating a rejection of a disabled identity. However, exposure to the perspectives of others, particularly the expressed sympathy and

negativity surrounding her amputation, appears to have triggered a shift in her self-perception. These external viewpoints, laden with societal assumptions about disability, may have contributed to a transformation in her outlook.

This shift is clearly reflected in her own words: "My body grew numb as I sat there petrified, knowing that everyone had somehow come to a consensus that death was the better option to living with one hand." This quote highlights the emotional toll of internalizing societal biases. It underscores the power of external narratives to undermine a person's sense of agency and hope.

Furthermore, Parvathy Gopakumar 's belief that "If adults were of the opinion that my life was going to be worse than death, then it must be true, I thought," reveals the vulnerability of a child navigating societal expectations. Her limited life experience makes her susceptible to the perceived wisdom of adults, leading to an uncritical acceptance of their opposing viewpoints. This idea reinforces the notion that disability becomes a social construct, not an inherent limitation, but rather a perception imposed by societal norms.

Gopakumar 's experience emphasizes the complex relationship between disability and social perception. It demonstrates how well-meaning but potentially damaging external narratives can erode an individual's initial resilience and lead to the internalization of negative biases about disability. This highlights the importance of making every effort to make it a point that stories belong to people who have disabilities and they will choose the stories that they want to tell to avoid stereotypes in society.

Gopakumar 's narrative illuminates the stigmatizing experience of becoming a visible symbol of disability within her community. The phrase "brand new disabled person" underscores her sudden transformation into a focal point of attention and speculation. Her description of being observed, discussed, and approached with various degrees of sensitivity or insensitivity highlights the intrusive nature of being viewed as a spectacle. The unsolicited advice she received further emphasized her otherness and created a sense of isolation, suggesting that the prevailing societal narratives about disability were often unhelpful and condescending.

The subsequent exposure to motivational inspiration videos reveals a pervasive societal assumption that women with disabilities inherently destine for a life of depression. These media representations often perpetuate harmful stereotypes by reducing complex human experiences to simplistic narratives of overcoming adversity. Such portrayals can inadvertently contribute

to a culture that expects individuals with disabilities to conform to specific, often narrow, expectations of resilience and positivity.

The pervasive association of disability with depression, particularly among women, is a deeply ingrained societal construct. These preconceived notions shape societal expectations and, consequently, influence self-perception. Parvathy's query, "whether I'd be able to be the ideal Bharatiya naari with only one hand," encapsulates the internalization of such societal pressures. Indian culture often imposes specific gender roles upon women, and the addition of disability is perceived as further deviating from these norms.

The responses Parvathy received from her community exemplify the process of social disabling. This refers to how society, through its attitudes, structures, and practices, creates barriers and limitations for individuals with disabilities. By imposing restrictive expectations and denying opportunities, society actively contributes to the construction of disability as a deficit.

Lennard J Davis finds a direct connection between the social process of disabling and industrialization. In fact, 'the social process of disabling' is the byproduct of industrialization. He says:

“the social process of disabling arrived with industrialization and with the set of practices and discourses that are linked to late eighteenth- and nineteenth-century notions of nationality, race, gender, criminality, sexual orientation, and so on.”
(Davis,24)

Parvathy Gopakumar's statement, "I yearned for attention so that I could show them how cool I was. I even used to make sexist, racist and homophobic comments, thinking that a mean girl image would be better than a sad disabled one," reveals a complex struggle with internalized ableism. Internalized ableism refers to the unconscious or conscious acceptance of negative societal attitudes about disability.

Here, Parvathy exhibits a clear binary: "mean girl" versus "disabled woman." This choice suggests that she perceives negative social perceptions associated with disability as more oppressive than those associated with being a rebellious "mean girl." The "mean girl" persona, in this context, becomes a subversive resistance against societal expectations for women, particularly those within patriarchal cultures. However, it is crucial to acknowledge the problematic aspects of this choice.

While the "mean girl" may challenge some social norms, she is often ostracized and labelled as a "fallen woman" – the antithesis of the idealized "angel in the house" archetype. This highlights the limitations of such rebellion within a larger framework of gender inequality.

Parvathy's ironic preference for "mean girl" over "disabled" further underscores the societal construction of disability as inherently undesirable. Parvathy's statement, "as I was afraid that I would attract more pity than I was already getting," underscores the pervasive societal tendency to view individuals with disabilities as objects of pity. This emotional response is often positioned as a crucial component of the social construction of disability, reinforcing stereotypes and marginalizing individuals with impairments.

Parvathy explains her phase of acceptance of disability as “It was harder than figuring out how to cut the fingernails on my remaining hand by myself and much harder than learning to tie my shoelaces.” She says, But, constantly tried to accept her as her. She claims that “In the initial years of being a disabled person, all I wanted was to prove was that I wasn’t one. ” and She gradually started to accept reality and began to see herself as normal and as part of society, rather than as ‘other’.

“Gradually, I tried to detach myself from the toxic things I was doing in my life. After years of constantly denying who I was and trying to fit in with the rest of the world, embracing my true self wasn’t easy at all.”

Parvathy's narrative offers an in-depth exploration of the complex interplay between physical disability and psychological well-being. Her journey of self-discovery marked by a prolonged period of denial and a desperate attempt to conform to societal expectations. The challenges associated with adapting to a new physical reality are juxtaposed with the even more arduous task of accepting a transformed identity.

Parvathy concludes her narrative by emphasizing a significant shift in perspective. She acknowledges a departure from the previously held desire to project an image of effortless adaptation to her disability. This transition reflects a journey towards self-acceptance and a reclamation of bodily autonomy. By highlighting mundane yet empowering acts, such as “storing chocolate in her prosthetic arm or applying nail polish to the silicon fingernails”, Parvathy redefines the boundaries of her body and challenges societal expectations. These actions symbolize a process of reclaiming and reimagining her physicality, transforming it from a source of shame or inadequacy into a site of personal agency and creativity.

Conclusion

The emergence of digital humanities has undoubtedly transformed the literary world, creating an accessible platform for diverse voices and narratives. Digital authoring has enabled people such as Parvathy Gopakumar to communicate their experiences to the rest of the world through the publication of their stories, which was not possible before.

Parvathy's essay, "Fake it till you make it," featured in Shreya Ila Anasuya's edited collection, "Skin Stories: Essays on Sexuality, Disability, and Gender," exemplifies the power of personal narratives in challenging societal norms and stereotypes. Through her detailed exploration of disability, identity, and resilience, Parvathy contributes significantly to the growing body of literature that interrogates the complexities of human experience. By analyzing this essay within the framework of digital humanities, this paper has demonstrated how digital platforms can facilitate the analysis of marginalized voices, ultimately contributing to a more inclusive and equitable society.

Parvathy Gopakumar's memoir recounts her experiences as a disabled woman, offering readers insights into the self-representation of disabled women in India. By deconstructing societal norms and challenging stereotypes, she provides a nuanced perspective on the challenges faced by individuals with disabilities. Gopakumar's work highlights the intersectionality of disability with other marginalized identities, such as gender. Her memoir offers a powerful counter-narrative and contributes to a broader understanding of disability representation in Indian literature.

The intersection of digital humanities and literature is a dynamic and evolving field. As technology continues to advance, it is vital to have its potential to amplify marginalized perspectives and create a more just and equitable world.

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